

A Study On Work Life Balance Among Employees In Ncs Sugars Limited

Vizianagaram

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Abstract-Work-life balance is concept creating and maintaining supportive and healthy work environments, which will facilitate employees to have balance between work and personal obligations and thus make stronger employee loyalty and productivity. Work life balance is gradually becoming a common talk. When employees go back to their homes, they should not carry any organizational stress with them. An individual has two roles to play personal and professional; each role having different set of demands. When such role demands overlap, multiple problems are faced leading to losses for all concerned: the individual, the family, the organization and the society. This investigative research is an attempt to study the work life balance issues with reference to employees in NCS sugars. The results derived from data analysis disclose significant results with respect to work life balance. The study has broad implications for industry in particular. The findings have significant implications for understanding, interpreting, and utilizing the contemporary work at sugar industries.

Key Words: work-life balance, multiple factors, work life equilibrium, employee loyalty

INTRODUCTION

An increasing number of studies have projected the importance of work–life balance. This analyzed the existing concern within custom and organizations about the impact of multiple roles on the health and well-being of professional and its implications regarding work, family performance, and citizen’s role in society. The following factors effected the experience of work–life balance were identified while reviewing the international literature.

- The many roles performed by citizen
- Role strain experienced because of multiple roles, i.e., role difference and role overwork
- Organization culture and work dynamics: Corporate values supporting work–life balance have constructive work and personal well-being consequences
- Personal possessions and social support: A number of studies confirmed the positive relationship between personalities, emotional support and well-being
- Career orientation and livelihood in which citizen careers need to be viewed in the context of their life course and time lines
- Coping and coping strategies: Women use both exciting and problem-focused coping strategies to deal with role divergence.

MEANING OF WORK LIFE BALANCE

Life is a balancing act, and in American society, it is safe to say that almost everybody is looking for work/life balance. But what precisely is work/life balance. We heard the term work life balance, complain that we are not having enough of it in our lives. Among men and women are trying search for work/life balance is a frequent topic of conversation, usually translated into not sufficient time and/or support to do, to handle, to manage our work commitments or personal obligations.

ROLE OF WORK–LIFE BALANCE

A growing number of articles have promoted the importance of work–life balance. This is things to see the current concern within society and corporate about the force of multiple roles on the health and well-being of professional women and its implications regarding work and family performance, and women's role in society. The following factors influencing to understanding of work–life balance were identified as reviewing the worldwide literature.

- The several roles performed by employees.
- Role pull experienced because of several roles, i.e., role difference and role overload
- Corporate custom and work dynamics: Firms values are very much influenced work–life balance have positive work and personal consequences.
 - Individual resources and communal support: numerous studies established the positive relationship between personalities, exciting support and comfort.
 - Career direction and career phase in which women careers need to be viewed in the background of their life course and time appearance.

NCS Sugars Limited is leading Sugar Company under the NCS Group of Companies, was established on the 6th June, 2002. NCS Sugars Limited is one of the sugar factories of the erstwhile Nizam Sugars Limited, a state-owned sugar factory, acquired by the NCS Group. The factory operations under the new management of NCS Sugars had commenced on 17th January 2003.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, a review of selected research work conducted in this subject matter is mentioned. Moncrieff et al (1997) was observed the precursors and consequences of salesperson job strain. According to authors, there are a number of organizational variables including met expectations, role conflict, role vagueness, job satisfaction, organization commitment and aim to leave which influence job anxiety.

Crooker et al (2002) to understand the relationship between life intricacy and Life is a balancing act, and in American society, it is safe to say that more or less everybody is seeking work life balance. But what accurately is work/life balance, all heard the word, and many of us complain about our lives.

McDowell (2004) has explained the ways in which corporate and institutions function at a range of balance as well as new sets of obligations towards co-workers, members of domestic and common in general. Wilkinson (2008) expressed a research. It was fulfilled that the adverse impact of an imbalance between work and personal or family life is emotional fatigue, pessimism and be exhausted.

Increasing role of women, especially mothers in the employment is largely attracting attention of work-life balance, both nationally and internationally. Until the 20th century the question of work-life balance was considered as unproblematic and the author considers two assumptions for this, one is that the standard worker was full time and it was usually male who worked full time and the other assumption is that women were involved largely in the domestic chores of life and unpaid work of labor caring. Thus, there was no problem of work-life balance since the work was equally divided between men and women, though in the 21st century, these assumptions have undergone a huge transformation as now women's employment has taken up the space.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What are the major factors that influence to work life balance?
- Do factors such as Gender, Age, Working Hours, Remuneration, Family Back Ground and Physical factors on Work Life Balance.
- Which factors influences much to work Life Balance at different levels of management.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objectives of study are as follows:

- To study and analyze the major factors that influences to work-life balance among the employees in NCS sugars.
- To understand how various factors that contribute to work life balance varied with different demographic profiles.
- To bring out strategies to improve the effective of work and life balance in NCS sugars.

HYPOTHESES

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the given null hypotheses are to be tested:

- ❖H₁: There is no significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Gender.
- ❖H₂: There is no significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Age.
- ❖H₃: There is no significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Working Hours of the selected organization.
- ❖H₄: There is no significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Family life.
- ❖H₅: There is no significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Personnel Life.

METHODOLOGY

It is an investigative study for the purpose of looking into work-life balance of employees employed in NCS sugars in Vizianagaram. The study was done in April-December 2016. There were 300 respondents selected. All of them were married male incumbents having one or two children. It was a simple, non-probability sampling that comprised of employees. As a result, the information were free to pursue those matters they considered important. The collected information was analyzed using simple percentage analysis and using statistical tools and techniques namely Correlation and Chi-square test. In order to get the results, statistical software such as MS- Excel and SPSS has been used. Charts and Figures had been prepared for presenting and simplifying the process of analysis.

ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Gender		Marital Status	Category	Age (In Years)		
	Male	Female			Married	Unmarried	
	240	60	282	18	128	158	14
	80	20	97	3	42	53	5
	Having Children		Work Experience (In Years)				
	Yes	No	0-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	Above 40
	282	18	164	76	35	18	7
	94	6	55	25	12	6	2
	Work Schedule				Partner Employed		
	Day Shift	Afternoon Shift	Night Shift	Rotating Shift	On-off Shift	Yes	No
	120	80	40	50	10	15	285
%	40	20	10	27	3	5	95

Source: Field Survey

Inference: Table-1: It indicates that out of 300 selected sample 240(80%) male and 60 (20%) are female and 97 percent sample are married. 94 percent of sample have children. Working scheduled of the company; Day shift 40 percent, after noon shift 20 percent, 27 percent rotating and 10 percent are working night shift.

Table 2: Employees Perception towards Family Life

Dependent adult					
	2hrs	2-4 hrs	4-6 hrs	bove 6 hrs	Total
Number	46	154	82	18	300
Percent	1552		27	6	100
Dependent adult					
Number	150	76	63	11	300
Percent	50	25	21	4	100

Source: Field Survey

Inference: Table-2: It indicates that Employee perception on Family life: 52 percent of employees have spent 2-4 hours and 27 percent have spent 4 to 6 hours to their family.

Table: 3 Employees' Feeling in relation to Time Spent on Work

the amount of time	py				appy
No. of Workers	51		27	9	12
Percent	17%	67%	9%	3%	4%

Source: Field Survey

Inference: Table-3: Employee perception on time spent on work: 17 percent of people felt extremely happy and 67 percent employees felt happy.

Table4: Perception of employees towards Work Life

Perception of Employees					Very often
work during off -duty period.			28%	26%	13%
y time with family due to work p			27%	13%	0%
ssed because of work			37%	9%	2%
k on job takes away personal in		3%	39%	13%	4%
mily for being preoccupied with			26%	8%	3%
peers dislike being preoccup			12%	4%	3%
al life while at work.					
because of personal work at hon			10%	4%	4%
akes up time which otherwise			14%	5%	3%
at work.					
nterferes with getting to work on			18%	3%	3%
ressed trying to balance your v			26%	11%	6%
life?					

Source: Field work

Inference: Table-4: Employee perception of employees towards work life: It is seen above 50 percent of employees agreed there is no work pressure during course of employment and 15 percent of employees felt seldom, 10 percent of employees agreed often and 20 percent of employees agreed sometime.

Table:5 Factors Affecting Work and Family Commitment

	No. of employees	Percentage
Long Working hours	72	24%
Shift Work	63	21%
Compulsory overtime	18	6%
Meeting/Training after office hour	72	24%
Other	75	25%

Source: Field Survey

Inference: Table-5: it is seen from above table 34 percent of workers have long working hours, 21 percent of have shift work and 24 percent have meeting/training and 25 percent of workers are specified other reasons.

Table 6: Do you Spend Time for Working out?

State of Nature	No. of employees	
Yes	192	64%
No	108	36%

Source: Field Survey

Inference: Table-6: It is seen from the table 64 percent employees spent time for workout

Table: 7Preferred Place to Workout

	No. of employees	Percentage
Residence	15	5%
Workplace	99	33%
Public Place	48	16%
Home	108	36%
Other	30	10%

Source: Field Survey

Inference: Table-7: Employee perception on place to work: 33 percent of customers are residence and 36% preferred to working.

Table: 8 Tools for Managing Stress Arising from Work

	No. of employees	Percentage
Agreed Entertainment	69	23%
Expressed Poor	72	24%
Agreed Entertainment	138	46%
Expressed Poor	24	8%
Agreed Entertainment	48	16%
Expressed Poor	18	6%

Source: Field Survey

Inference: Table-8: Managing stress from work 46 percent of workers agreed entertainment and 44 Percent are expressed poor.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

This chi-square measures to compare a collection of definite data with some hypothetical expected distribution. It is a statistical test commonly used to compare observed data with data we would expect to obtain according to a specific hypothesis. The chi-square test is testing the null hypothesis, which explained that there is no difference between the expected and observed result. This point of study is to find the impact of work life balance of workers to their personnel life in selected sugar company have taken five hypotheses, which are tested by using chi-square test by considered demographic variables and other variables:

The formula for calculating chi-square = $(O - E)^2 /$
 Table- 9

Testing of hypotheses between Work Life Balance and Personnel Life

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

	Hypothesis			Hypothesis Result	
	o significant relationship Life Balance and Gender.			Rejected	0.000
	o significant relationship Life Balance and Age			Rejected	0.000
s	o significant relationship Life Balance and Working			Rejected	0.013
	o significant relationship Life Balance and Family I			Accepted	0.423
	o significant relationship Life Balance and Personne			Rejected	0.037

* Significant at 5% level, the result is not significant at $p < 0.05$.

Source: Computed

Inference: It can be seen from the above table it shows the chi-square values of given five hypothesis; all the hypotheses are rejected except hypothesis four, which is accepted at 5% level of significance it indicates that age, gender, working hours and personnel life factors are influenced the work life balance, whereas family life factors is influenced the work life balance in NCS Sugars Limited.

Discussion

For decades, work-life balance has been a very important issue for society, and even now, when most of us are quick enough to connect with what matters the most, an vast relation between what we say matters most and the way we actually spend our time. In present sugar company, there are several departments where every employee is responsible to handle various job prospects for their collective output, that is, exploration of oil and gas. Many employees are highly dedicated to their work that they give very little time to their families resulting in work-family conflict. However, it is probable to be successful, while at the same time maintaining a balance between one’s private and professional lives. The findings of present study:

- ❖ It was observed that most of the workers were happy and worked sincerely. However, there is useful for a supportive system to address the work-life conflicts, as there was a mixed response regarding the same.
- ❖ 54% of the employees were of the opinion that NCS Sugars supported its employees to promote better work-life balance.

- ❖ It is found that 84% of the respondents felt happy with their work and they felt that at any time there is a call during odd hours, it gave them an impression that it is a call from work.
- ❖ 23% of the employees said that even during holidays, they were unable to mentally disconnect from work, and often worried about work as revealed in the Table. Hence, mentally also, they had to plan their prospect course of work.
- ❖ It can be seen that 60% of the respondents missed out on any quality time with family because of work pressure.
- ❖ It is observed that age, gender, working hours and personnel life factors are influenced the work life balance, whereas family life factors is influenced the work life balance in NCS Sugars Limited

The following are suggestions to promote work/life programs:

- ❖ Align work/life initiatives with HR strategy, Create a work/life award program introduce noncash incentives associated with business objectives.
- ❖ It is suggested that superiors frequently interacted with their subordinates and discuss their difficulties and give proper direction for effective work balance environment.
- ❖ It could be suggested that Self-management strategies are to follow by the workmen that successfully using the spaces in our lives is very important, and that available resources, time, and life are limited.
- ❖ Time management is improved through appropriate goals and judicious. It gives significant importance to best and when, and assembling the appropriate tools to achieve exact tasks.
- ❖ By nature, community tend to become more multifaceted over time. In the face of increasing difficulty, stress on the individual is to be expected.
- ❖ It is suggested that well managing skill means ensuring that knowledge and experience serves you, rather than degrade you. Knowledge has always protected the balance the work life.
- ❖ It should be suggested that employer will provide recreation facilities and work pressure to be minimised with proper control.

Conclusion: The findings of the study, the employees of the NCS Sugars Limited had a good work-life balance, but a lot more needs to be done in line with the present scenario of globalisation, as now, companies has realised the significance of work-life balance, companies must offer suitable environment that is conducive for work-life balance is to grab the talent and will be able to retain the employees. This study suggests the there is a requirement to have a customised work-life balance policy considering the age group of the present working force. In addition, it is believed that rigorous research must be continued to provide the necessary independence perspectives in the direction of potential solutions.

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